

Combined categories Brexit

Anti Muslim

01 Anti-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [negative trait]')

02 Anti-Muslim, specific (extremism, evil, radicalisation, anti-Quran, anti-Islamic scripture etc)

04 Islamification/ spread of Islam (Cultural clash, censorship, Islam taking over the world, conversion, attacks on 'our' culture, country, Shariah law, references to the movement of refugees, Muslim problem, cultural deviance)

05 Scapegoating Muslims for Brexit

06 Islamophobia id denied/exaggerated

Supporting Muslims/ other minority groups

11 Pro-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [positive trait]')

12 Pro-Muslim, specific (contribution to society, acts of kindness, religion of peace, scientific endeavours etc)

13 Muslims are victims/ discrimination/racism/ Islamophobia

15 Racism in British politics

16 Racism in US politics

Anti-right politics

23 Anti Conservative/right agendas

24 Pro Labour/ left agendas

27 Anti far right agenda

29 Anti white supremacy

34 Pro LibDem

41 Left-wing criticism of mainstream media

Anti-left Politics

- 22 Pro Conservative/right agendas
- 25 Anti Labour/ left agendas / anti 'woke'
- 26 Pro-far right agenda
- 28 Pro white supremacy
- 35 Anti LibDem
- 42 Right-wing criticism of mainstream media

03 Terrorism

30 Immigration

Politics

- 14 Brexit and anti-Muslim politics (eg blame politicians, globalisation, economics, social structures etc)
- 21 Politics, general
- 32 Relating Brexit to Indian politics
- 33 Relating Brexit to US politics

Other

- 31 Community relations/cohesion
- 43 Tweet disseminates/premised on conspiracy theory
- 44 Tweet identifies/alleges conspiracy theory
- 45 accusation of antisemitism
- 46 antisemitism in content
- 99 Other

